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Three Month Employment Expectations in Europe

Decreased on average of 3.09% between March 2022 and December 2022

The Eurostat calculates the value of expectations on employment in the coming months. The indicator is produced by the Management for Economic and Financial Affairs of the European Commission. It takes into consideration four different corporate sectors or industry, services, retail trade and buildings. The indicator provides an indication of the variations of employment in European countries. The indicator is calculated as a weighted media, the expectations of the managers about the occupation in the four sectors analyzed. The long -term indicator is placed equal to 100. Values greater than 100 mean that managers believe that employment expectations are higher than in the long run. Values lower than 100 indicate that managers expect a lower employment value than long -term trend.

Ranking of the countries by value of the indicator of expectations on employment in the next three months. Bulgaria is in the first place due to the value of expectations on employment in the next three months with a value of 115, followed by Croatia with a value of 112.6 and Slovenia with a value of 111.7 units. In the middle of the standings there are Belgium and Albania with a value of 105.3 units followed by Greece with a value of 105 units. Poland closes the ranking with a value equal to 94.5 units, followed by Estonia with a value of 93.1 units and by Denmark with a value of 82.8 units.

Ranking of the countries by the percentage variation of the percentage of employment expectations at three months. Northern Macedonia is in first place for the value of the percentage variation of the three -month employment expectations with a value of 12.47% equal to a value of 11.6, followed by Turkey with a value equal to 8.4% equal to an amount of 8.6 units and from Cyprus with a value equal to 7.81% equal to an amount of 7.8 units. In the middle of the standings there are Romania with a value equal to -2.07% equal to an amount of -2.2 units, followed by France with a value equal to -2.99% equal to -3.3 units, e From Spain with a value of -3.43% equal to an amount of -3.7 units. Ireland closes the ranking with a value of -11.19% equal to an amount of -12.3 units, followed by Finland with a value of -17.17% equal to an amount of -19.8 units and from the Denmark with a value equal to -28.87% equal to an amount of -33.6 units.

Clusterization with K-means algorithm optimized with the silhouette coefficient. Below is a clusterization with K-means algorithm optimized with the silhouette coefficient. Two Clusters are then identified or:

- Cluster 1: Latvia, Estonia, Poland, North Macedonia, Lithuania, Cyprus, Denmark, Czech Republic;
- Cluster 2: Finland, Hungary, Montenegro, Turkey, Spain, France, Malta, Greece, Belgium, Albania, Germany, Austria, Romania, Bulgaria, Sweden, Croatia, Slovakia, Serbia, Slovenia, Italy, Portugal, Netherlands.

From the point of view of the median, it is possible to verify the existence of the following system or of the Clusters or $C2 = 107.3 > C1 = 98.5$. The analysis therefore shows that the countries of Northern

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Europe and some Baltic countries have lower employment expectations compared to other European countries.

Network Analysis with Manhattan's distance. A network analysis is then presented below with the use of Manhattan's distance. The analysis shows the presence of a complex network structure composed of the following connections:

- Romania has a connection with Italy for a value of 0.56, with Slovakia for a value of 0.64 units and with Serbia for a value of 0.51 units;
- Italy has a connection with Romania for a value equal to 0.56 units, with Slovakia for a value of 0.31 units, with Serbia with a value of 0.55 units and with Portugal for a value of 0.77 units;
- Slovakia has a connection with Romania for a value of 0.64 units, with Italy for a value of 0.31 units, with Serbia for a value equal to 0.7 units and with Portugal for a value equal to an amount of 0.85 units;
- Serbia has a connection with Romania for a value of 0.51 units, with Slovakia for a value of 0.7 units, with Italy for a value of 0.55 units and with Portugal for a value equal to 0.84 units;
- Portugal has a connection with Italy for an equal value of 0.77 units, with Slovakia for a value of 0.85 units, with Serbia equal to a value of 0.84 units, with Slovenia equal to an amount of 0.77 units, with the Netherlands equal to an amount of, 0.72 units;
- Slovenia has a connection with Portugal for a value of 0.77 units, with the Netherlands for a value of 0.6 units, with Bulgaria equal to a value of 0.72 units;
- The Netherlands have a connection with Portugal for a value of 0.72 units, with Slovenia equal to an amount of 0.6 units and with Sweden for a value of 0.74 units;
- Bulgaria has a connection with Slovenia for a value of 0.72 units and with Croatia for a value of 0.65 units;
- Croatia has a connection with Bulgaria for a value of 0.65 units.

Network analysis allows you to analyze the propagation effects of the variable observed without inferential the presence of a causal link. For example, if the value of three -month employment expectations grow (or decrease) in Slovenia of one unit then employment expectations at three months grow (or decrease) also in Portugal for a value equal to 0.77, in the Netherlands for a value of 0.6 and in Bulgaria for a value of 0.72.

Conclusions. Between March 2022 and December 2022 employment expectations at three months on average decreased by an amount of -3.09%. There are countries in which the value of employment expectations has significantly decreased such as: Denmark with -28.87%, Finland with -17.17%, Ireland with -11.19%. Above all, the countries of Northern Europe have a reduction in employment expectations to three months. The reduction of three -month employment expectations is a serious fact since it manifests what are the expectations of hiring European managers. Managers believe that in the coming months there will be a reduction in employment. The fact that this reduction is more marked for the economies of northern Europe, which are also more connected and internationalized, could be an indicator of a more marked slowdown in the occupation which could subsequently spread also in central, southern, and oriental Europe.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

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Appendix

Aspettative di Occupazione a Tre Mesi. Fonte: Eurostat										
Country	2022-03	2022-04	2022-05	2022-06	2022-07	2022-08	2022-09	2022-10	2022-11	2022-12
Belgium	★ 110,7	★ 110,8	★ 107,1	★ 110,5	★ 107,7	★ 108,9	★ 101,9	★ 105,3	★ 98,6	★ 105,3
Bulgaria	★ 108,3	★ 112,5	★ 109,3	★ 113,1	★ 110,1	★ 111,1	★ 112,1	★ 111,4	★ 112,5	★ 115
Czechia	★ 105,3	★ 106,8	★ 103,1	★ 102,3	★ 103	★ 102,2	★ 100,4	★ 99,5	★ 99,6	★ 98,5
Denmark	★ 116,4	★ 107,1	★ 106	★ 96	★ 97,9	★ 99,3	★ 100,1	★ 92,9	★ 93,8	★ 82,8
Germany	★ 110,3	★ 111	★ 113,1	★ 111,5	★ 107	★ 106,8	★ 104	★ 100,8	★ 104,6	★ 104
Estonia	★ 102,5	★ 100,8	★ 101,9	★ 100	★ 97,2	★ 97,5	★ 96,3	★ 94,5	★ 94,3	★ 93,1
Ireland	★ 109,9	★ 104,4	★ 107,8	★ 98,5	★ 94,8	★ 100,1	★ 99,1	★ 93,4	★ 95,8	★ 97,6
Greece	★ 110	★ 104,7	★ 108,2	★ 110,8	★ 110,2	★ 102,6	★ 104,3	★ 99,8	★ 109,6	★ 105
Spain	★ 108	★ 106,5	★ 108,1	★ 106,8	★ 104	★ 106,8	★ 103,8	★ 103,3	★ 104,5	★ 104,3
France	★ 110,3	★ 109,7	★ 108,1	★ 104,5	★ 101,1	★ 104,7	★ 107,4	★ 107,5	★ 107,7	★ 107
Croatia	★ 108,4	★ 111	★ 107,8	★ 115	★ 108,2	★ 108,5	★ 110,1	★ 110,2	★ 111,1	★ 112,6
Italy	★ 107,7	★ 109,1	★ 110,5	★ 110,6	★ 110,3	★ 108,3	★ 106,2	★ 106,2	★ 108,3	★ 109,6
Cyprus	★ 99,9	★ 96	★ 103,7	★ 102,1	★ 98,7	★ 97,3	★ 103,6	★ 105,2	★ 103,3	★ 107,7
Latvia	★ 99	★ 99	★ 98,1	★ 96,5	★ 98,3	★ 98,6	★ 97,3	★ 96,5	★ 98,2	★ 100,4
Lithuania	★ 99,8	★ 101	★ 99	★ 102,8	★ 103,2	★ 102,8	★ 101,5	★ 100,1	★ 100	★ 99,7
Hungary	★ 108,3	★ 110,2	★ 107,2	★ 107,2	★ 109,9	★ 104,5	★ 103,9	★ 99,4	★ 100,4	★ 104,2
Malta	★ 113,6	★ 105	★ 117,6	★ 117	★ 113,7	★ 116,7	★ 99,5	★ 112,6	★ 98,3	★ 107,6
Netherlands	★ 114	★ 114,2	★ 112,5	★ 112,2	★ 109,8	★ 110	★ 108,1	★ 107,9	★ 108,3	★ 108,3
Austria	★ 115,9	★ 114,2	★ 107,4	★ 112,7	★ 112,6	★ 105,9	★ 109,6	★ 104,5	★ 103,9	★ 107,6
Poland	★ 96,5	★ 98,5	★ 99,4	★ 98,9	★ 94,3	★ 95,8	★ 94,2	★ 93,3	★ 93,8	★ 94,5
Portugal	★ 112,1	★ 111	★ 110,8	★ 109,8	★ 109,8	★ 109,4	★ 108	★ 106,5	★ 111,7	★ 110,3
Romania	★ 106,3	★ 108,8	★ 110	★ 110,5	★ 107,8	★ 105,8	★ 106,4	★ 108,2	★ 108,3	★ 104,1
Slovenia	★ 112,4	★ 113,9	★ 111,5	★ 113	★ 110,6	★ 111,7	★ 109,6	★ 110,1	★ 111,2	★ 111,7
Slovakia	★ 108,1	★ 108,9	★ 109,1	★ 110,4	★ 110,9	★ 107,4	★ 105,2	★ 105,2	★ 109	★ 106,5
Finland	★ 115,3	★ 112,8	★ 112,9	★ 107,3	★ 103,8	★ 98,6	★ 99,7	★ 98,6	★ 98,4	★ 95,5
Sweden	★ 115	★ 114,6	★ 113,7	★ 112,4	★ 111,2	★ 109,2	★ 106,2	★ 105,6	★ 103,6	★ 103,2
Montenegro	★ 104,9	★ 106,9	★ 101,7	★ 108	★ 102,8	★ 104	★ 106,4	★ 109,6	★ 112,2	★ 111,1
North Macedonia	★ 93	★ 88,3	★ 94,6	★ 92,8	★ 98	★ 98,1	★ 90,5	★ 89	★ 105,2	★ 104,6
Albania	★ 116,2	★ 113,3	★ 123,9	★ 118,8	★ 114,8	★ 110,2	★ 114,5	★ 105,9	★ 107,9	★ 105,3
Serbia	★ 108,3	★ 110,5	★ 110,6	★ 109,6	★ 106,3	★ 107,9	★ 106,2	★ 107	★ 108,1	★ 107,9
Türkiye	★ 102,4	★ 104,2	★ 108	★ 106,7	★ 105,1	★ 105,9	★ 106,5	★ 108,8	★ 108,2	★ 111

